

**PRIORITY AREAS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
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The development of a corporate-level strategy covers all the resources of an educational institution

ABSTRACT

The development of market relations in our country, as well as the related intensification of competition in the higher education market, places before higher education institutions of the republic the task of solving theoretical and practical problems in a coordinated manner across a number of areas, as well as ensuring their competitiveness. These areas include.

The development of market relations in our country, as well as the related intensification of competition in the higher education market, places before higher education institutions of the republic the task of solving theoretical and practical problems in a coordinated manner across a number of areas, as well as ensuring their competitiveness. These areas include:

- studying the needs and demands of potential consumers of the products and services of higher education institutions;
- organizing monitoring of the higher education market in order to collect the necessary information;
- developing a generalized model project and a mechanism for ensuring competitiveness;
- establishing a logically sound management process aimed at increasing the competitiveness of higher education institutions as the main modern objective of their development;
- forming a general system of evaluation indicators and, on their basis, determining the level of competitiveness and analyzing its dynamics;
- identifying a set of general approaches to the quantitative assessment of competitiveness;
- developing specific methods, algorithms, and procedures for solving issues related to competitiveness.

In order to ensure the long-term sustainable functioning and continuous sustainable development of a higher professional education institution, the key to success is the coordination of the activities of all internal elements, the optimization and rationalization of interrelations among them, as well as the search for optimal relations with the external environment and the solution of issues related to ensuring competitiveness.

The main elements of the proposed system consist of managing the competitiveness of higher education institutions, identifying the necessary tools for this purpose, and assessing the current level of competitiveness and the effectiveness of its provision.

It is considered appropriate to use the marketing department as the body coordinating the entire set of activities aimed at ensuring competitiveness, and to assign the following functions to this department:

- analyzing the market conditions of higher education;

- assessing the competitiveness of higher education institutions and developing programs to maintain and improve its level;
- monitoring the obtained results.

In developing a system for ensuring the competitiveness of higher education institutions, the following methodological approaches to marketing activity may be taken as a basis:

- relying on the most important indicators that ensure the improvement of the competitiveness of higher education institutions;
- forming the results obtained from the assessment of the level of competitiveness and its components in terms of determining the degree of their impact on the marketing activities of the higher education institution;
- developing appropriate management decisions based on the results of the assessment.

The strategic goals and priority areas for determining the priority directions of systematic reform of higher education in our republic, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities who are capable of independent thinking to a qualitatively new level, modernizing higher education, and developing the processes of providing the social sphere and sectors of the economy with qualified personnel based on advanced educational technologies are defined in the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System until 2030.

Based on long-term target objectives, the development of the higher education system is carried out according to the following priority areas:

- expanding coverage of higher education and improving the quality of training specialists with higher education;
- introducing digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process;
- increasing the effectiveness of research activities in higher education institutions, widely involving young people in scientific activity, and forming the innovative infrastructure of science;
- increasing the effectiveness of spiritual, educational, and upbringing activities;
- actively involving personnel customers in the process of training highly qualified specialists;
- ensuring the financial independence and stability of higher education institutions and strengthening their material and technical support;
- systematically developing higher education institutions and improving management activities;
- introducing effective mechanisms for combating corruption and ensuring transparency;
- increasing the investment attractiveness of the higher education system and ensuring its international recognition and competitiveness.

Today, there remain a number of urgent problems and shortcomings in the higher education system that require solutions in the training of highly qualified personnel. These include the following:

- a) cooperation between higher education institutions and personnel customers in the training of personnel has not been effectively established, and the participation of employers in shaping the content of higher education is insufficient;
- b) students have not sufficiently developed skills in critical thinking, independent information search, and analysis;
- c) in the field of strengthening the material and technical base of higher education institutions:
 - the capacities of student dormitories, libraries, training workshops, laboratories, sports and recreation facilities, and social infrastructure facilities do not meet existing demand, and in most of them, a material and technical base meeting modern requirements has not been formed;

- the level of availability of educational and scientific laboratories equipped in accordance with modern requirements in higher education institutions is insufficient; the share of classrooms meeting international standards is only 10 percent. At the same time, the educational process is not sufficiently provided with laboratory materials, including reagents, chemical vessels, components, biological materials, and other objects;

- the main part of the financial expenditures of higher education institutions is spent on wages, while insufficient funds are allocated for updating educational and scientific laboratories and repairing buildings and facilities;

d) in the field of increasing the attractiveness of higher education and ensuring international competitiveness:

- none of the higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of the top 1,000 higher education institutions in internationally recognized rankings, and their official websites are not included in the top 1,000 list of the Webometrics international ranking;

- educational programs and criteria for assessing students' knowledge have not been fully adapted to international standards;

- existing student dormitories and social infrastructure facilities have not been adapted to the needs of foreign students;

- promotional activities aimed at widely attracting foreign citizens to study in our country, including PR projects such as organizing Days of Higher Education Institutions of Uzbekistan, holding presentations, and other activities, have not been organized at a sufficient level; in addition, there is no interactive virtual platform in this area.

The problems of managing the strategic development of higher education institutions include the following:

- the excessively global nature of the strategic goal;

- the insufficiency of the financial, human resource, material, and information base required for the implementation of the strategy;

- the insufficiency of necessary organizational and managerial innovations;

- the absence of a mechanism linking strategic and operational aspects in the management of higher education institutions, and others.

The analysis of the effectiveness of the activities of higher education institutions and their positioning in the global scientific and educational environment has made it possible to connect the level of success of their strategic management with the degree of manifestation of academic autonomy and the increasing density of state regulation.

An important factor is the formation of the content of strategic programs aimed at the development of higher education institutions based on the types of strategies and the factors influencing them, such as state policy in the field of education, demand for educational services, the level of competition, geographical location, size, stage of development, form of ownership, profile, and other advantages. It is also important to develop mechanisms for implementing the targeted projects and measures included in these programs, with clearly defined deadlines and responsible persons.

The above shows that the structure of a strategic development program for higher education institutions can be divided into the following areas:

- forming indicators for the training of specialists with higher education and optimizing educational fields and specialties;

- improving quality management, increasing the level of pedagogical activity, making targeted use of advanced teaching technologies, and improving educational and methodological support;

- ensuring the quality of scientific research and increasing the effectiveness of international cooperation;
- increasing the effectiveness of spiritual, educational, and upbringing activities;
- developing the financial activities of higher education institutions and strengthening their material and technical support.

In developing strategies for the development of higher education institutions, general attention should be paid to the following:

- improving the world through global citizenship education;
- promoting scientific inquiry;
- learning adaptability;
- internationalization;
- establishing relations with the business environment;
- developing infrastructure.

Taking into account the complexity of the educational environment, the following principles of strategy development may be used in modern higher education institutions:

1. Viewing strategic planning as a holistic approach: higher education institutions are considered as a single institution encompassing various forms of integrated and interconnected subsystems. The academic strengths of higher education institutions are based on broad organizational resources, including tangible, intangible, and semi-tangible resources. These resources are directed toward achieving academic excellence and competitive advantage.

2. Identifying target areas:

- corporate-level strategic goals are broad strategic goals by their nature. They are aimed at achieving competitive advantage;
- strategic goals specific to functional areas arise from corporate-level goals.

3. Creating a constructive educational environment and achieving academic excellence:

- services and facilities of higher education institutions, consisting of a combination of tangible, intangible, and semi-tangible resources;
- education, consisting of a combination of tangible, intangible, and semi-tangible resources;
- research, consisting of a combination of tangible, intangible, and semi-tangible resources;
- academic staff, representing intangible resources.

4. Identifying priority goal areas for improving academic excellence and organizational efficiency.

5. Supporting each target area through appropriate strategic initiatives and relevant quality assurance procedures aimed at improving the quality of education and competitive advantage.

The development of a corporate-level strategy covers all the resources of an educational institution. It may also include the development of specific plans for functional areas and combinations of resources. The general priority task for higher education management is to achieve competitive advantage in the global higher education market. This is characterized by increased competition between public and private higher education institutions to attract international students and researchers, research funds, and other resources.

The complexity, diversity, and various directions of the internal processes of higher education institutions cannot be described by any single universal indicator. Therefore, in order to ensure that the results obtained are complete and reliable, complementary indicators describing these criteria have been identified and grouped. The balanced set of these indicators makes it possible to comprehensively assess the competitiveness of higher education institutions. In addition, identifying internal reserves and achievements, involving them in institutional activities, and

forming a monitoring information base represent the necessary tools and, ultimately, the most advantageous competitive position.

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